

Interview with Virginie Rozée

Permanent Researcher at INED.

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1. What strengths do you see in the partnership between B²-InF and INED?

I see four strengths in the partnership between B²-InF and INED: (1) the issue covered by the project, (2) the international and collaborative dimension of the project, (3) the material conditions and resources offered by the project, and (4) the intended impact of the project.

INED has been working on infertility and ART issues for several years, even decades. It has significant expertise on these issues in France. Therefore, the project fits with the scientific work of INED, especially within its research unit "Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights". It provides additional expertise, considering other European countries, other target populations (young people, people who are not directly concerned by infertility and ART), and another research focus (the offers made by the clinics). These issues have not been so far addressed in INED research projects.

Then, INED is very involved in European research and committed to developing international projects, with partnerships from different countries, disciplines and sectors. These collaborations broaden the field of expertise and knowledge on a given issue or population; they allow global and transversal analysis.

The B²-InF project fits in with this determination to develop cooperative, multi-disciplinary and multi-sectoral projects. Indeed, the project is simultaneously conducted in eight European countries, including Eastern Europe countries, which are generally under-investigated in European research projects. It also brings together 10 European partners, from universities, associations, from public and private sectors, with a different expertise area and discipline.

On a more material and logistical level, B²-InF allows the partners to carry out the research in good conditions and support. One of the important objectives of INED is training in research through research. The project provides an opportunity to meet this objective as INED plans to hire a post-doctoral fellow to participate in this research.

Finally, for INED, the impact of the research in society is essential. Disseminating knowledge is indeed one of its main missions. The objective of B²-InF is to formulate recommendations based on the research results in order to inform those working in ART field (medical doctors, policy makers, civil society), to make them adapt their policies, activities and communication to be more in line with the expectations of the younger generation. Thus, the project perfectly fits with INED mission to inform social debates and policy decisions.

2. How is the purpose of this project in relation to INED?

INED is particularly involved in infertility and ART issues in the French context, where, until recently, access to ART was particularly restricted (only to heterosexual couples, for some techniques only), where infertility is still an invisible or even taboo social matter, and where fertility awareness is a very recent topic. Through our studies, we have observed an important gap between the expectations / demands of the population and the legal and medical possibilities regarding ART.

However, research at INED, like most of the research conducted on the subject around the world, mainly focuses on experiences of patients or on medical practices and offers. Very few studies explore ART knowledge and representations in the general population. These issues are nevertheless primordial to better approach and understand infertility social experience for the people concerned and the public's preconceived ideas about these recent techniques (which can lead to misunderstandings and even discrimination).

The project offers the scientific and material resources to explore all these questions at the European level, including countries that are little studied internationally. The purpose of this project is therefore to bring the INED's expertise, but above all to feed our own research and projects with the knowledge that B²-InF will bring but also with the way it is carried out, with the original methodologies and collaboration that are deployed.

I think it is the first Science with and for Society (SwafS) project conducted at INED. Therefore, we have a lot to give but also a lot to learn (even if we have a very solid International Affairs and Partnerships department).

3. Is the young society's perception towards fertility and treatments a topic of importance for INED? Why so?

At INED, many research and surveys are conducted on young people, including their sexual and reproductive lives. However, none of these studies address their perceptions of infertility and ART. Indeed, very few studies explore ART knowledge and representations in the general population, i.e. in ART non-users and people who are not, a priori, infertile. We know even less among young adults.

B²-InF will bring new knowledge to these young people, by questioning them for the first time on their knowledge and expectations regarding ART.

The results of this project will enlighten public debates, including in France, by showing the gap or, on the contrary, the match between the expectations of young people and the medical and legal possibilities in their country; young people being the future ART users and the future social actors and decision-makers.

4. The voice of society is important in this domain. Why do you think it has been relatively neglected so far?

The voice of society in the domain of infertility and ART is neglected because this issue is essentially seen as a medical one (in fact, most of the research on the subject is in the field of medicine or public health). Also because it is considered as a marginal issue, touching very few people in the general population, and as a deviant issue from the dominant social norms.

Yet, this issue concerns everyone, since it questions our representations of procreation, family formation and parenthood. This also raises questions about the normative conditions for creating a family (what we call in France the "procreative norm"), which mean that many people who want children wait until these conditions are met before conceiving a child. However, infertility is also related to the age of the future parents, both for women and men.

5. What is your opinion about the project? Method, team combination, strengths and goals?

In my opinion, B²-InF project is an important and original project. It develops an international, intersectoral and multidisciplinary approach.

Indeed, the project is simultaneously conducted in eight European countries and brings together an international team working in different but complementary fields and sectors.

Then, the project proposes a legal, gender and socio-cultural research perspective, which will allow an original global and transversal analysis. It is also a very innovative project since it analyses the offers made by the clinics, through their advertising (websites, flyers, etc.), in order to observe whether they correspond to people's expectations.

Finally, the pragmatic aspect makes the project much-needed and essential. It aims to enlighten those working in the ART field, including policy makers, so that they can adapt their policies, medical offers, practices and communication and make them better fit with the young generation's expectations.

On a more personal and human ground, the team is very nice; the meetings are very friendly and give rise to many exchanges.

B2-InF Stage 1: Complete

B2-InF Stage 1, the Data Collection phase is complete. The process was two-fold. On the one hand, interviews collected noteworthy data about ART's concerns of young people aged 18 to 30 from 8 European countries (Spain, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Kosovo, Albania, Macedonia, Slovenia) about ART. On the other hand, well-defined and in-depth research was conducted to collect data from clinics about what they share on their web pages.

For the first, between 10 to 15 interviews were planned in each country with men and women 18-30 years old, nationals or migrants living for more than ten years in the country, childless and not ART users. Purposeful sampling was defined for each country following the previous criteria aiming to capture the diversity of each country considering the following variables: age, gender, sexual orientation, occupation, educational level, residence, relationship status, marital status and religious beliefs. The socio-demographic characteristics of young people interviewed were collected in templates specifically designed. Besides, an ad-hoc template was designed to collect the information on the fieldwork of each country. This information was collected by fieldwork teams conducting the interviews in each country. All the interviews were conducted in national languages, audio recorded, literally transcribed, and translated into English.

Prior to writing the report, a literature review was conducted through the consultation of academic databases aiming to describe and summarize the context of each country related to assisted reproduction technology. The information extracted was added to the knowledge and information provided by the fieldwork teams. The information collected was then verified through a validation workshop in each of the sample countries, and the data was confirmed for the next stage: the data analysis stage.

For the second point, between 3 to 5 clinics were planned to be explored in each country, aiming to collect the information supplied by the clinic's websites and the 'physical information' (e.g. leaflets, informed consent forms) provided by the selected clinics. Purposeful sampling was defined following the following criteria: various company sizes, variety of ART offered and geographical diversity. The sample excluded those companies that work as intermediaries or do not provide direct clinical services.

'Physical information' was collected by downloading PDFs available on the websites or requesting more information from the clinics by email or phone call. The information available on the clinic's website was collected in the native language of the country in templates specifically designed for it and afterwards translated into English. Data collection was carried out by [Medistella](#) (B2-InF partner).

Kristien Hens: The Ethics of Comprehensive Chromosome Screening

On the 1st of April, Kristien Hens, Research Professor at the University of Antwerp and PI of the gender analysis part of B2-Inf held a lecture at the ESHRE campus course on Genetic counselling in preimplantation genetic testing (PGT), a course that took place from 31st of March till 1st of April online. The course was aimed at healthcare professionals in PGT who wish to learn about genetic counselling.

Professor Kristien Hens talked about the interviews she had conducted for research with couples undergoing preimplantation testing for translocations between 2016 and 2018 at UZ Brussels. She used open-ended interviews and analyzed them in NVIVO.

Recurrent themes were the burden and benefit of the procedure with microarray, the difficulty of defining the good life, and the professional's role. After the presentation, some time was spent reflecting on the need for information about the impact of disability and the need to incorporate experiences of disability infertility practice.

She also presented the B2-Inf project, describing its purpose and goal to close the gap in knowledge between Fertility treatments providers and the broad society.

Add-ons and “therapeutic illusion”

First of all, what are Add-ons?

They are optional additional treatments, also referred to as 'supplementary', 'adjuvants' or 'embryology treatments' offered by fertility clinics claiming to improve the chances of having a baby through assisted reproduction technologies. Of course, each of these treatments is added to the fertility cycle for an additional cost, varying from 100 euros to thousands of euros. Nevertheless, the evidence to support the reliability and effectiveness of these treatments is often missing or non-reliable.

Due to assisted reproduction technologies' inevitable low success rate, clinics often use add-ons to create a customer loyalty program to keep patients as clients. This way, patients enter a vicious emotional cycle that pushes them to try again and again when the standard treatment has failed, with different add-ons. What drives them is the hope of success.

It is essential to ascertain whether these add-on therapies' improvement compared to the standard procedure is based on scientific evidence and whether their success rates are true to their promise. In the ethical reflections on assisted human reproduction, there is a term called "*therapeutic illusion*", which refers to this reality.

Many organizations, such as B2-InF's consortium partner **Fertility Europe**, has long been fighting to improve the information provided to patients in order to avoid falling into this illusion.

The lack of transparency and regulation is part of the core reasons why the B2-InF project exists, which is interested in analyzing the information that clinics are offering to society and improving them according to society's needs and expectations, also allowing governments to act well informed.

Next Steps

Socio-cultural, gender, and legal experts from B2-InF are currently analyzing all the information collected during the project's first phase. This consists of a content analysis of both the interviews done with the young population (18-30 years of age) and the information provided by the leading ART clinics in the 8 European sample countries (Spain, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Kosovo, Albania, Macedonia, Slovenia).

This analysis will provide the necessary information for the elaboration of 8 national recommendation guidelines that will aim to guide all stakeholders involved in ART (mainly industry, scientific associations and governments) to a fundamental improvement of the information offered to society and align their practice with the expectations, concerns and knowledge of the young population.

After the first elaboration of the guidelines, we will have an internal workshop to discuss the drafts. Then, we will have a validation workshop to validate the guidelines, involving all the stakeholders. After that, the project's third and final stage will consist of strategic dissemination of the guidelines.

